

Heat Show Tour Development Model in Wukirharjo Village, Parengan District Tuban District, Indonesia

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Abstract: This study aims to explain the management of the concept of pristine tourism and involve stakeholders, this research can be viewed from the concept of governance approach with the research focus being tourism management with indicators of Attractions, Facility, infrastructure, Transpiration, and Hospitality. The method used is a qualitative approach. Data and information obtained by means of interviews, documentation, and observation. Intake of research informants used purposive and snowball sampling techniques, in the research process, 24 informants were inventoried primary data sources. In analyzing using interactive data analysis techniques Miles and Huberman's model, which states that "activities in qualitative data analysis are carried out interactively and take place continuously until complete. Activities in data analysis, namely data reduction, data display and conclusion drawing/ verifying". The results of this study indicate that, the Government in this case, Perum Perhutani Parengan and stakeholders have carried out several processes in running tourism, namely attractions, facilities, infrastructure, transportation and hospitality.

Keywords : Development Model, Nature Tourism, Wukirharjo Village

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is currently a necessity for people at various levels, not only for certain circles, so that the handling must be done seriously and involve the parties concerned. In addition, to achieve all tourism development goals, promotions must be held so that the potential and tourist attraction can be better. Known and able to mobilize potential tourists to visit and enjoy tourist attractions. In this case the tourism industry is competing to create tourism products that are more varied regarding the preservation of the object it self in accordance with the objectives of tourism development, namely to introduce natural beauty, cultural customs and diverse customs (Sutedjo, 2007), (Yoeti, 1996), (Pitana, 2005).

Tourism can also provide a direct impetus to the progress of the construction of ports, roads, local transportation, hygiene or health programs, pilot projects of cultural facilities and environmental sustainability and so on (Spilane, 1985). All of which can provide benefits and pleasure for both the community in the area concerned and for foreign visitors. Tourism can also provide encouragement and contribution to the implementation of development projects in various sectors for countries that have developed or developed economies, which in turn the tourism industry is a reality in the midst of other industries (Pendit, 2002), (Sharpley, 2002), (Gamal, 2002).

According to Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning tourism, tourism is a travel activity carried out by a person or group of people by visiting certain places for recreational purposes, personal development or studying tourist attractions that are visited temporarily. Tuban Regency is a Regency that is rich with tourism potential. This potential is in the form of natural tourism and cultural tourism, this is stated because almost every area in the Regency increases regional income. In addition to providing benefits to the region, tourism can also provide direct benefits for the local community. One of the sub-districts in Tuban Regency is Parengan District.

Parengan district is an area that has a tourist attraction with promising natural beauty. The famous tourist attraction in Parengan District is the Prataan Hot Spring Tour which is managed by Perum Perhutani Parengan, the Prataan Hot Spring Tour is located in Wukirharjo Village, Parengan District, Tuban Regency, East Java Province.

Since the discovery of hot springs originating from Mount Kadeng in 1990, it has been made a tourist attraction by the local village community, but in 2015 the tour was taken over and managed by Perum Perhutani Parengan. There are also facilities provided by the parengan hot spring tour, namely 10 privacy soak rooms, 3 swimming pools, toilets, canteen, fish therapy, outbon spots, campgrounds, prayer rooms, and also interesting selfie spots.

Farazmand (2004) Problems related to the governance of Prataan Hot Springs Tourism in Wukirharjo Village are the managers who are less professional, marked by the poor service available in Prataan tourism. Sources obtained from the results of initial observations by way of interviews with tourists who are in tourist objects, about the complaints of services felt by visitors and the absence of involvement of third parties, namely private parties (observation march 2020).

The access road to the bathing location is also quite far from the city center and the narrow road conditions and up and down hills, especially through the forest in deserted conditions, make visitors anxious if they want to visit prataan tours. In infrastructure tourism, the infrastructure is inadequate, such as the lack of a "gazebo" resting place. The facilities in the swimming pool are also not equipped with water slides or other water rides. Some visitors feel disappointed because there are no facilities that complement the tour.

The tourism development is photographed with the indicators of Attractions, Facility, infrastructure, Transpiration, and Hospitality. The purpose of this paper is first to describe what potential can be developed to increase tourist interest in hot spring tourism. The second is to describe what efforts are made by Perum Perhutani in managing plain tourism in order to increase the number of tourists. As for the research question, how is the governance model for hot springs tourism in wukirharjo village.

II. METHODS

The type of research used is descriptive research with a qualitative approach. This research is located in Tuban Regency. The focus of this research is tourism management with indicators of Attractions, Facility, infrastructure, Transpiration, and Hospitality. Intake of research informants used purposive and snowball sampling techniques, in the research process, 24 informants were inventoried primary data sources. Sources of data used are primary data sources and secondary data by means of observation, in-depth interviews and documentation (Sugiyono, 2011). In analyzing using interactive data analysis techniques Miles and Huberman's model, which states that "activities in qualitative data analysis are carried out interactively and continue continuously until complete. Activities in data analysis, namely data reduction, data display and conclusion drawing/verifying" (Moleong, 2013).

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Attractions

In tourism the role of attraction is very important because it can attract the attention of tourists or visitors, for that tourist attraction is divided into 3 namely natural attractions, cultural attractions, man-made attractions in accordance with the statement of tourism managers.

Natural attraction

Judging from the natural attractions, hot springs from Mount Kadeng which are believed to cure skin diseases, the cold water source comes from Watu Wagar which gives a sensation of natural freshness without bleach, and the scenery around tourist sites is still beautiful.

Cultural attraction

The culture of the Wukirharjo village community, which is still thick with the manganan tradition (Alms of the Earth) makes this tradition more interesting by presenting wayang art performances. The place where this tradition takes place is in the location of the prataan hot springs because the community believes that this

location provides extraordinary benefits to the people of Wukirharjo village. Not only that, every weekend there is always an entertainment stage for tourists and a community.

Man-made attraction

The development of a tour cannot be separated from human intervention, namely the addition of permanent buildings such as stalls/shops, toilets, stages, and others. The addition of buildings is not enough, but also from tourist attractions such as the procurement of various types of properties to increase tourist attractions, such as places for various selfie spots. Some tourists visit this location to take pictures and seek entertainment, some do activities to enjoy the facilities that are already available, such as swimming in hot water, swimming, fish therapy, picnics, outbans, and taking pictures. Every 6 months the tour manager makes improvements by distributing questionnaires with the aim that the tourism manager can find out the lack of tourism. There are no routine tourism activities, but the manager provides a place for activities from outside tourism.

Facility

The facilities are more directed at the existing infrastructure in tourism prataan. Most visitors are interested in coming by considering adequate infrastructure facilities, some people find out the desired facilities before visiting the tourist area to be visited. Therefore, Perum Perhutani Parengan seeks to improve facilities.

Every year this tour experiences many changes in terms of facilities and is always growing. The new innovation that Perum Perhutani Parengan created is the addition of a children's playground called Agro Education, where children can play and learn at the same time. Obstacles faced by tourism managers are hilly soil conditions with a fairly steep slope, rocks, and funding constraints (costs) that make parks for children not realized.

Infrastructure

Infrastructure can be described as a system of physical facilities that support the life, sustainability and economic and social growth of a society or community. The infrastructure referred to in this study refers to the availability of tourism supporting infrastructure such as irrigation/water systems, electricity and energy sources, communication networks, sewage/water disposal systems, and health services.

As explained earlier, the role of infrastructure is an important aspect in achieving development, both in the social and economic fields. The role of infrastructure is also a very important element because the development of available infrastructure and infrastructure systems will be able to encourage the tourism sector. For this reason, the tourism manager has provided a safety guarantee in the form of life insurance in the event of an incident or accident, this hot spring tourism also provides various health services because this tour is included in the category of health-based tourism.

Transpiration, firstly, access to the prataan hot spring is quite far from the city and the road conditions pass through a steep and narrow hill. Even so, along the way, visitors can enjoy the natural beauty, green hills and mountains that are still beautiful. The problem is that visitors have to bring their own vehicles because there are no public transportation routes to get to this place. Along the road every 100 meters, there are signboards for its function so that visitors do not get lost due to conditions in the middle of the forest, besides that many trees are cut down because they are considered to interfere with the journey. The road conditions at tourist sites are very bad and uphill if visitors, for example, are not familiar with the road conditions, it can lead to accidents while driving. The next stage is planning for road repairs.

Hospitality, the friendliness of the villagers of Wukirharjo, the tourism sector. It will not be far from social interaction between local people and tourist visitors. The community will interact with the local community as an initial introduction. With good communication and interaction between local people and tourists, it will increase the number of visitors or tourists. Therefore, the crowds of visitors make local people take advantage of it as an addition to their income or their economy, starting from paying tourist entrance tickets, opening small businesses and other profits. However, there are some tourist officers who act impolitely towards visitors and make the visitors feel annoyed with the officers.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Perum Perhutani Parengan as the main actor of tourism organizers, namely mobilizing, fostering, empowering and providing the role of each stakeholder. The people of Wukirharjo village are allowed to sell at the location and the officers there are also given special training to get quality human resources. Cooperating with the Wukirharjo village community by establishing the Tani Makmur institution and also plans to add facilities for children's playgrounds so that the tour is not only a health tourism event but also a recreation. Hot Spring Tourism includes road access, network and the absence of a children's play area, but various existing problems are already under repair, such as: road access has been repaired for a 200-meter road. the communication network has provided wifi capacity but does not cover the needs of visitors, the last one is a children's game vehicle, namely the addition of a ball bath and future plans for making a children's playground, but the problem is the sloping ground condition. Steep and rocky make the implementation of development has not been implemented.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author would like to thank the Head of the Public Administration Study Program, Dean of the Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Chancellor of Bojonegoro University for his support in this research.

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